

Complementary Material for the Paper Understanding Undesirable Attributes of Requirements Engineers: Insights from Practitioners

1. RESEARCH METHOD

We followed a method based on the work of Kalliamvakou et al. [1] and Dias et al.[2]. For answering the research questions, we surveyed software practitioners to identify desirable and undesirable attributes of requirements engineers, interviewed a subset of them to gather more details about each attribute, and asked the interviewed participants a follow up question to identify the level of importance of the strategies to become a great requirements engineer.

The following subsections present the data collection and analysis procedures for each step of the research method for undesirable attributes.

1.1. Survey on Attributes of Undesirable Attributes Requirements Engineers

a) Design and Data Collection

The survey comprises a set of characterization questions and an open-ended question for participants indicating up to five attributes they considered detrimental to performing RE activities. We asked only up to five attributes because individuals usually pay more attention to the top few choices, mitigating additional noise in lower rankings [10]. Focusing on just five attributes would (i) keep participants from running their response, (ii) require them to provide focused responses, discarding less relevant attributes, and (iii) reduce the cognitive load of remembering specific past experiences.

b) Data Analysis

We applied different data analysis procedures, as the survey is composed of closed and open-ended questions. For closed questions, the number of participants choosing an option was calculated and then summarized the participants' characterization. For open-ended questions, we examined the list of attributes provided by participants to identify similarities, i.e., two or more attributes have the same meaning. This process was essential as we did not provide participants with a pre-defined list of attributes. The coding process was performed by the first and second authors. Initially, they individually coded the transcripts and then reviewed each other. Later, they met with the last author to resolve differences.

We also perceived that the attributes are related to each other, allowing us to group them into categories. The categories are based and adapted on those defined by Dias et al. [4] For example, we used communication category to group the attributes: difficulty in relationships, lack of communication, lack of interaction with development areas, inaccurate, not listening to all stakeholders. The grouping process was performed using constant comparison [colocar citação] and was performed by the first author and reviewed by the last author.

1.2. Follow up Interview

a) Design and Data Collection

As shown in Figure 1, we defined the interview script in two sections. In the *opening* section, the participant provided his/her definition for great software requirements engineer and described characteristics of a great one that he/she has worked with. In *attributes of a bad software requirements engineer* section, the participant defines, explains why such an attribute

is considered bad, and how it can be avoided with the use of three attributes. Although each participant provided up to five attributes in the survey, we selected the three highest-ranked attributes from their list.

We conducted the interviews remotely, with each lasting around 30 minutes and recorded with the participant's permission.

Section	Interview question (IQ) description
Opening	We present the informed consent term.
	IQ1. In your words, how would you define a great software requirements engineer?
	IQ2. Have you ever worked with a great software requirements engineer?
Attributes for a bad requirements engineer	IQ3. Why did you consider him/her a great requirements engineer?
	In the survey, you listed five undesirable attributes for a bad requirements engineer. Now, let us address three of them: <<attributes a, b, and c>>.
	IQ4. How would you define attribute a?
	IQ5. Why is attribute a bad for great software requirements engineers?
	IQ6. How can a requirements engineer avoid attribute a?
	IQ7-IQ9. Same questions for attribute b.
	IQ10-IQ12. Same questions for attribute c.

Figure 1: Interview script.

b) Design and Data Collection

We transcribed the interviews and sorted the responses by question. We then coded each transcription to capture the main ideas in participants' answers [5], [11]. For example, participant P1 reported the following answer to IQ1: *"the issue of communication is important, because it has to be a person who knows to listen and intervene at the right times (soft skills), and from a technical point of view, it is more important to know the domain."* In this example, we found the following codes: *communication, listening skills, intervention at appropriate time, interpersonal skills, and domain knowledge*. The coding process was performed by the first and second authors. Each of them, individually, coded half of the transcripts and then revised each other. Afterwards, they met with the last author to resolve the divergences.

The codes extracted from the definition of attributes reported by participants in IQ4 are concepts. We applied conceptual mapping over the concepts to identify relationships between the attributes. Therefore, we assumed that these attributes are interconnected. The first and second authors carried out this process and then met with the third author to review the results.

2. THREATS TO VALIDITY

Like any empirical study, there are potential limitations and threats to the validity of our methods and finding [3].

Construct validity: We conducted a survey with software requirements engineers and software project managers to identify undesirable attributes. However, the participants did not explain these attributes in the survey. During the interviews, participants had the opportunity to elaborate on their meanings. Although the definitions were elicited later, the participants recognized the attributes identified in the survey, reducing the threat of inconsistent interpretations.

External validity: Our analysis consists entirely of 18 software practitioners from the software development industry in one country, which may limit the relevance of our results to the broader population of software managers and requirements engineers. To reduce this threat, we included participants with varied experience levels, company size, and Professional experience. Another threat to external validity is the potential lack of interaction some participants may have had with truly exceptional software engineers, rather than those who are just competent. To address this, we asked participants to justify their views on what makes a software engineer undesirable, based on the attributes they defined. Furthermore, since our domain is closely tied to information systems, we made efforts to include participants from other areas, such as the commercial and financial sectors, to mitigate this limitation.

Internal validity: Threats to internal validity may arise from the questionnaire. Since it was administered remotely, participants could have misinterpreted the questions. To mitigate this threat, the questionnaire had two internal validations, one external validation, and a pilot study. Another potential threat is related to the use of the term "undesirable requirements engineer" in the questions. Participants could have misunderstood this term, which might have led to invalid responses. To address this threat, we reviewed all answers to SQ10 and concluded that no invalid responses were provided.

Conclusion validity: A potential threat arises from the qualitative analyses we conducted, as they involve a subjective process. To mitigate this threat, the analyses were performed separately by two researchers with a consensus achieved by an experienced researcher. Additionally, we applied the constant comparison technique when coding the interview transcripts, continuously comparing our findings with previous ones as they emerged during the data analysis. Another threat to conclusion validity relates to the participants' project roles. While we acknowledge the importance of requirements engineers in the context of this study, we did not survey only practitioners performing requirements-related tasks. Including participants with managerial roles was also crucial, as it provided us with a more comprehensive understanding of the attributes of an undesirable requirements engineer.

REFERENCES

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